

Multi-performance shape memory epoxy resins and their composites with narrow transition temperature range

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Background

Shape-memory polymers (SMPs) and their composites are an emerging class of functional materials capable of sensing stimuli from changes in external environment and responding to such changes by recovering to a predetermined state. They are widely used in aerospace, biomedical, and other fields. In particular, thermosetting shape memory epoxy resins (SMEPs) have been studied.

SMEPs

1 Aerospace

2 Engineering

3 Information

Highlights

- A series of SMEPs with narrow T_g range (14-23°C).
- Added ETBN formed a sea-island structure
- Combining two-stage curing technology

Result and Discussion

Dynamic mechanical analysis

Mechanical performance

Shape memory performance

Design of Crosslinked Network

Construction of homogeneous chain segments, π - π strong cross-linked network

Conclusion

- A series of SMEPs and their composites with narrow T_g range (14-23°C).
- The added ETBN formed a sea-island structure, which increased the elongation at break by 4 times.
- Combining two-stage curing technology, the T_g, modulus and strength of the system were improved.